

Isovanillin Isonicotinoylhydrazone and its Metal Complexes with Transition Metals

VANITA PURI and BADRI V. AGARWALA*

Department of P. G. Studies and Research in Chemistry, R. D. University, Jabalpur-482 001

Manuscript received 31 October 1995, revised 20 September 1996, accepted 10 January 1997

The tuberculostatic activity of isonicotinic hydrazide and its aroylhydrazones containing azomethine nitrogen is attributed to their ability to form stable complexes with *d*- and *f*-block metal ions¹. The present communication reports the study of the metal complexes of biologically active ligand^{2,3}, isovanillin isonicotinoylhydrazone (IVINH).

Results and Discussion

The nmr spectrum of the ligand indicates the presence of donor sites and that the compound exists in the keto form. This observation is in conformity with its ir spectral data.

Analytical data (Table 1) support 1 : 2 metal-to-ligand stoichiometry for the complexes with dipositive Co, Ni, Cu, Zn and tripositive Ce cation. The presence of lattice/ coordinated water and coordinated acetate is supported by TG and ir spectral data.

TABLE I—ANALYTICAL AND PHYSICAL DATA OF IVINH (LH) COMPLEXES*

Compd. no.	Compd.	Colour	Metal% : Found/ (Calcd.)
1a	[Co(L) ₂ (H ₂ O) ₂].H ₂ O	Brown	8.3 (8.8)
3a	[Ni(L) ₂ (H ₂ O) ₂].H ₂ O	Orange	8.6 (8.7)
4a	[Cu(L) ₂ (H ₂ O) ₂].2H ₂ O	Brown	9.2 (9.7)
5a	[Zn(L) ₂ (H ₂ O) ₂].2H ₂ O	Yellow	9.2 (9.6)
6a	[Ce(L) ₂ (OAc)(H ₂ O)]	Yellow	17.9 (18.5)

*All compounds gave satisfactory C, H and N analysis; m. p. > 360° for all compounds.

Ir spectra : The phenolic-OH group of IVINH does not take part in coordination as ν_{OH} band (3300–3400 cm^{-1}) remains unchanged on complexation. The metal complexes are characterised by the presence of a band at 1560–1580 cm^{-1} ($>C=N-N=C<$) which is absent in the ligand spectrum³. The $\nu_{C=N}$ ligand band is lowered by 30–45

cm^{-1} in the spectra of the complexes, indicating the involvement of one azomethine nitrogen in coordination⁴. Further, appearance of ν_{M-N} band at 350–450 cm^{-1} supports the above proposition^{5,6}. The ligand band at 3244 cm^{-1} (NH) disappears on complexation. The ligand band at 1653 cm^{-1} (C=O) disappears on complexation and new band appears in the complexes⁶ at 1360–1380 cm^{-1} (C–O enolic). The appearance of ν_{M-O} band 550–450 cm^{-1} in the complexes shows oxygen linkage by deprotonation of enolic oxygen.

In the Ce^{III} complex, the additional bands at 1600 and 1420 cm^{-1} (ν_s and ν_{as} COO) indicate coordination of the acetate ion. The acetate ion functions as an unidentate ligand as shown by $\Delta\nu = 180 \text{ cm}^{-1}$. Appearance of new bands in far-ir region at 357–437 (M–N) and 460–487 cm^{-1} (M–O) shows that the ligand IVINH is monobasic having two coordination sites, i.e. azomethine nitrogen and enolic oxygen.

Magnetic susceptibility : Cobalt(II) has magnetic moment of 5.2 B.M. expected for d^7 -system in a high-spin configuration commensurate with octahedral geometry⁷. The theoretical spin-only magnetic moment for octahedral nickel(II) complexes is 2.83 B.M., but it falls in the range 2.9–3.3 B.M. due to spin-orbital contribution. The μ_{eff} value (3.34 B.M.) of Ni^{II} -IVINH complex supports octahedral geometry. This is consistent with the value of 3.23 B.M. noticed for octahedral $\{\text{Ni}(\text{H}_2\text{O})_6\}\text{SO}_4$ complex commensurate with the presence of two unpaired electrons. The magnetic moment of Cu-IVINH complex (2.09 B.M.) lies in the range of octahedral geometry.

Electronic spectra : Out of the three well-known spin-allowed transition bands for an octahedral cobalt(II) complex, the Co^{II} -IVINH complex exhibits ν_3 band at 22 727 and ν_1 at 10 256 cm^{-1} . These are consistent with octahedral geometry around Co^{II} ion. The values of the ligand field parameters B' , ligand field splitting energy, $10Dq$ and ν_2 for Co^{II} -IVINH complex has been determined as 920, 11585 and 21842 cm^{-1} respectively. The values of ν_2/ν_1 (2.12) and ν_3/ν_1 (2.21) are close to that observed for high-spin hexaaquacobalt(II) chloride complex⁸. The value of B Racah parameter and percentage lowering B^0 are calculated to be 0.95 and 5% respectively.

In Ni^{II} -IVINH octahedral complex, the values three spin

*Since deceased.

allowed ν_1 , ν_2 and ν_3 transitions observed at 10416, 18748 and 26315 cm^{-1} respectively, are in good agreement with Ni^{II} octahedral complexes⁹. The value of ν_2/ν_1 (1.79) is in agreement with the theoretical value for octahedral complex. The values of ν_1 and ν_3 is in good agreement with transitions obtained in octahedral Ni complex⁸. $\{\text{Ni}(\text{salicylaldehyde-furoic acid hydrazide})(\text{H}_2\text{O})_3\}^{11}$. Ni-IVINH complex has $10Dq$ of 10416 cm^{-1} and P 11518 cm^{-1} . Other parameter B , B' and B'' are calculated.

Cu-IVINH complex reveals three transition bands at 10416, 11363 and 12500 cm^{-1} as normally observed in Cu^{II} d^9 -system due to Jahn-Teller distortion, which are in good agreement with the values reported for Cu^{II} octahedral complexes¹⁰.

Thermal analysis : The Co^{II} complex of IVINH first undergoes dehydration with loss of weight at 50–130° corresponding to two molecules of water. These water molecules are present in the crystal lattice. At 130–220° there is 10.5% weight-loss corresponding to one molecule of water. Loss of water upto 220° confirms its coordination to metal.

It is concluded from the above discussion that ligand IVINH acts as a monobasic bidentated ligand and coordinates through its enolic form to yield largely 6-coordinate octahedral metal complexes. In the Ce^{III} complex, the water molecule is replaced by acetate group.

Experimental

Isovanillin, isonicotinic hydrazide, dimethyl formamide (all Sisco), $\text{Co}(\text{CH}_3\text{COO})_2 \cdot 4\text{H}_2\text{O}$, $\text{Ni}(\text{CH}_3\text{COO})_2 \cdot 4\text{H}_2\text{O}$, $\text{Zn}(\text{CH}_3\text{COO})_2 \cdot 2\text{H}_2\text{O}$, $\text{Cu}(\text{CH}_3\text{COO})_2 \cdot \text{H}_2\text{O}$ (all E. Merck) and $\text{Ce}(\text{CH}_3\text{COO})_3$ (Samir Tech.) were used. Ethanol and other solvents were of A.R. grade.

Microanalysis was performed on a Hitachi 2000 instrument. Magnetic susceptibility was measured by Faraday's method at Panjab University, Chandigarh. Ir spectra (CsI) were recorded on a Hitachi 270 spectrophotometer, diffuse reflectance spectra on a Varian-Cray 2390 spectrophotometer and ^1H nmr spectrum (DMSO-d_6) on a Bruker AMX-400 FT nmr spectrometer using TMS as internal standard at Indian Institute of Science, Bangalore. TGA and other methods were the same as described earlier³.

Ligand IVINH : A solution of isovanillin (0.05 mol, 7.60 g) in ethanol was added to an ethanolic solution of isonicotinic hydrazide (0.05 mol, 6.86 g) and the mixture

was refluxed on a water bath for 3–4 h. The resulting yellow solid formed on cooling was washed with ethanol, ether and subsequently dried over CaCl_2 : (Found : C, 61.58; H, 4.92; N, 16.01. $\text{C}_{14}\text{H}_{12}\text{N}_3\text{O}_3$ calcd. for : C, 62.01; H, 4.79; N, 15.49%); δ 8.76 (H-8, H-9), 7.81 (H-6, H-7), 9.33 (proton exchanged with D_2O , H-5), 8.31 (H-4), 7.07 (H-1), 6.99 (H-2), 7.29 (H-3), 3.81 (OCH_3), 11.88 (OH).

Metal complexes : Aqueous solution of the metal salt (0.005 mol) was added dropwise to a solution of IVINH (0.01 mol, 2.71 g) in DMF (50 cm^3) with constant stirring and heating. The total volume of the mixture was raised to 100 cm^3 by adding ethanol. The mixture was then refluxed over a heating mantle for 4 h. The resulting bright coloured complexes were washed with alcohol followed by ether and dried under reduced pressure over CaCl_2 .

Acknowledgement

The authors are thankful to Prof. C. L. Khetrapal, Bangalore, for providing nmr facility, to Dr. S. K. Sharma, Chandigarh, for magnetic measurements and to U.G.C., New Delhi, for financial assistance to one of them (V.P.).

References

1. W. SHAOZU, H. YOUHONG, Z. YULAN and W. HUI, *Synth. React. Inorg. Metal-Org. Chem.*, 1994, **24**, 583.
2. S. HINGORANI and B. V. AGARWALA, *Transition Met. Chem.*, 1993, **18**, 576.
3. B. V. AGARWALA, S. HINGORANI, V. PURI, C. L. KHETRAPAL and G. A. NAGANAGOWDA, *Transition Met. Chem.*, 1994, **19**, 25.
4. V. M. LEOVAC, L. S. JOVANOVIC, L. J. BJELICA and V. I. CESLJEVIC, *Polyhedron*, 1989, **8**, 135.
5. I. U. KHAN, S. K. SRIVASTAVA and S. C. SRIVASTAVA, *Indian J. Chem., Sect. A*, 1987, **26**, 238.
6. K. NAKAMOTO, "Infrared and Raman Spectra of Inorganic and Coordination Compounds", Wiley-Interscience, New York, 1978.
7. N. N. GREENWOOD and A. EARNSHAW, "Chemistry of the Elements", Pergamon, New York, 1985.
8. C. DAUL, C. W. SCHLAPFER and A. V. ZELEWSKY, *Struct. Bonding*, 1979, **36**, 129.
9. A. SYAMAL and R. L. DUTTA, "Elements of Magnetochemistry", Affiliated East-West Press, New Delhi, 1993; J. E. HUHEEY, "Inorganic Chemistry", Harper, 1983.
10. A. B. P. LEVER, "Inorganic Electronic Spectroscopy", Elsevier, Amsterdam, 1968.